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To Evaluate Cerebral Infarction Among Hypertensive Patients on Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Ayesha Abdul Rauf Toor¹, Anmol Abdul Malik¹, Zunaira Ghouri¹, Aliza Nadeem¹, M. Ahmad Nisar¹, M. Gulraiz Khan¹, Hasham Hanjra¹, Humaira Rauf¹

¹ University Institute of Radiological Sciences and Medical Imaging Technologies, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, The University of Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan

Abstract

Background: cerebral infarction among Hypertensive patients is very common that increases the complications of mortality in later age. This study aimed to rule out cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients on Magnetic resonance imaging. **Objective:** To Evaluate cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients on MRI. **Methods:** The study will be conducted in 162 hypertensive patients including both Male and female. To assess Cerebral infarction it will be acquired on MRI **Results:** we separated the subjects on the basis of their age (40-91 years). We grouped the same subjects on the basis of their sex (77 males, 47.5% & 85 females, 52.5%) calculating their frequency and percentage respectively. The mean values among the age of patients and the standard deviation in subjects is 67.35 ± 10.937 . The Frequency and percentage of patients complaining showed that vertigo (11.7%), Diabetes Mellitus (45.1%), Dementia (4.3%) appeared with Cerebral Infarction. We Produced a table where we separated infarction on the basis of NO infarction (53.7%) Numbers of infarction One (16.7%), Two (2.5%) and Multiple (27.2%) collectively (46.4%) Appeared with cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients. The results indicated that 46.4% appeared with cerebral infarction triggered by hypertension and that hypertension can be the cause of cerebral infarction and can lead to morbidity and mortality particularly in adults. **Conclusions:** These results show that hypertension can be the cause of cerebral infarction and can lead to morbidity and mortality particularly in adults. This study incorporates up to the minute data regarding cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients on magnetic resonance imaging it is the modality of choice for imaging cerebral infarction. It provided a trend that needs to be validated with further studies and analysis on a bigger population

Keywords: Magnetic Imaging Resonance, Cerebral Infarction, Perfusion Weighted Imaging, Diffusion-Weighted Imaging, Hypertension

Introduction

One of the most prevalent clinical cerebrovascular illnesses, cerebral infarction accounts for 60-80% of cerebrovascular illnesses. Cerebral infarction is the second major cause of death owing to its acute progression, rapid decline and severe cerebral edema complications (Liu H, 2011). Imaging is presently the most reliable strategy for cerebral infarction therapy. Diagnosis has advanced from traditional morphology to the mixture of morphology and function through the growth of contemporary medical methods and imaging technology, in particular, the advancement of MRI. Infarction can happen in the context of acute anemia, e.g., after Parvovirus

infection, risk factors include male gender, low hemoglobin, relative hypertension, hyposplenism laboratory proof, prior seizures and comparatively rare pain (Hurley MC, 2012). MRI using diffusion-weighted pictures (DWI) increases the capacity to diagnose acute cerebral infarction (CI) both in terms of absolute CI volume analysis and reliable CI location. MRI may also detect substantial occlusion or chronic stenosis of the cerebral artery. MRI enables the assessment of cerebral collateral flow and the imaging of reversible is chemical modifications (Sanak D, 2006). Diffusion-weighted (DWI) and perfusion-weighted (PWI) MRI are strong global methods for acute cerebral ischemia diagnosis (Tong D, 1998). Imaging with Diffusion weighted MR (DWI) indicates acute ischemic damage early after stroke (Hand P, 2006). Dr. Sarah E Vermeer and her fellows Research published in July 2007 concluded that MRI-defined silent brain infarcts among 20% of healthy elderly people and up to 50% of patients in selected series. Most infarcts are lacunes, of which hypertensive small-vessel disease is thought to be the main cause (Vermeer SE, 2007). According to D Renard in the reviewed article on Cerebral microblems: a magnetic resonance imaging review of common and less common causes published in Dec 9, 2017 concluded that Cerebral microblems (CMBs) are tiny foci of (acute, subacute or chronic) blood products, easiest seen outside iron deposit-sensitive magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) techniques (i.e., gradient-echo T2 * -weighted and prone). Often found in small vessel disease (SVD) (the most common conditions are hypertensive vasculopathy and cerebral amyloid angiopathy) and other illnesses as well (Renard D, 2018). According to C Kesavadas and his fellows research published on 2003 in a study concluded that Diffusion imaging has an elevated degree of sensitivity and specificity for acute brain ischemia diagnosis. Along with the imaging of perfusion. DWI helps to identify the diffusion territory-perfusion mismatch representing the penumbra of the operational ischemic. DWI pictures help to distinguish acute from subacute and chronic ischemic insults together with apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) maps. If early thrombolysis is instituted, the hyperintense region in DWI seen in acute brain ischemia can be inverted. DWI shows ischaemic abnormality. The latest MR methods have been created to reduce artifacts related to diffusion imaging (Kesavadas, 2003). According to R Rajeshkannan and his fellow members research published in 2006 concluded that Diffusion MR scanning has now become a regular element of brain MR imaging testing and is important in assessing patients with stroke. Furthermore, elevated signal intensity on MR diffusion and hypointensity on obvious co-efficient diffusion (ADC) pictures, characteristics of acute cerebral infarction, were revealed under such varied circumstances as hemorrhage, abscess and tumor (RajeshKannan R, 2006). According to S Bhagvati research published in 2013 in a study concluded that Multiple, concurrent, acute cerebral infarcts are generally secondary to embolic occlusion of various cerebral arteries in distinct arterial regions. A five-year retrospective review of all patients with numerous, near-simultaneous, acute cerebral infarction identified on diffusion-weighted MRI scans. Our research indicates that transient blood pressure decrease in high-risk hypertensive patients with serious, tiny vessel illness may sometimes lead to tiny, cerebral infarction (Bhagvati S, 2013). According to Sathoshi Hoshide Kazuomi Kario research published in 2001 in a study concluded that Lacunar mechanisms differ extensively, hypertensive small-vessel vasculopathy is regarded as the most prevalent cause of lacunar infarction (Hoshide S, 2001).

According to Fernando, research published in 2003 in a study indicated that (MRI) is an effective perfusion assessment method and plays a growing role in acute stroke inquiry (Calamante F, 2003).

Methods

It was a Descriptive study carried out in department of Radiology, Al-Razi health care center Lahore. The expected duration of study is from May 2019 to July 2019. The study was conducted on population with a sample size of 162. Both Male and female subjects were enrolled for examination on MRI Siemens 1.5T Magnetom. The approach used is the subject lying in the supine position. To assess Cerebral infarction, head scan were acquired by MRI. Hypertension was diagnosed to patients in the sitting position if patient blood pressure reached 160 mm Hg systolic/95 mm Hg diastolic. The collected data was stored in EXCEL, predesigned data collection sheets and SPSS software were used to apply relevant tests for statistical analysis. As the research follows scientific method, related information was taken from the recent articles and the references were given in the chapter of references.

Results

We calculated the mean values and the standard deviations of the data acquired. The mean values among the age of patients and the standard deviation in subjects is 67.35 ± 10.937 . The Frequency and percentage of patients complaining showed that vertigo (11.7%), Diabetes Mellitus (45.1%), Dementia (4.3%) appeared with Cerebral Infarction. We Produced a table where we separated infarction on the basis of NO infarction (53.7%) Numbers of infarction One (16.7%), Two (2.5%) and Multiple (27.2%) collectively (46.4%) Appeared with cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients. The results indicated that 46.4% appeared with cerebral infarction triggered by hypertension and that hypertension can be the cause of cerebral infarction and can lead to morbidity and mortality particularly in adults.

Table 1: Mean Among Age Of Patients

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	162	40	91	67.35	10.937
Valid N (listwise)	162				

The table shows the mean values of the parameters and the standard deviation. The mean recorded in total sample size was 67.35; the descriptive statistics had a minimum of 40 and a maximum 91 age of patients. The calculated hypertensive patients age estimated among Patients was as low as 40 and as high as 91. The mean values among the age of patients and standard deviation in subjects is 67.35 ± 10.937 .

Table 2. Frequency table of Hypertensive Patients

Gender	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	77	47.5%
Female	85	52.5%

Table 2: Table represents the frequency of Hypertensive males and females. The percentage of hypertensive females (85) in our study was 52.5 .while percentages of Males were 47.5, respectively.

Table 3: Frequency table of diabetes Mellitus Among Hypertensive patients**DIABETES MELLITUS**

DM	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	73	45.1%
No	89	54.9%

Table 3: Table shows 73 hypertensive Patients with 45.1% Having Diabetes Mellitus while 89 hypertensive patients 54.9% were non-diabetic.

The data showed that (46.4%) Appeared with cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients. And 53.7% of hypertensive patients appeared with no any form of cerebral infarction. Among the sample size the frequency of Dementia was very low 4.3% most of the hypertensive patients were without dementia 95.7%.

Table 4 : Frequency table of Vertigo among hypertensive Patients

Vertigo	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes	19	11.7%
No	143	88.3%

Table 4: Table shows 19 Hypertensive Patients with 11.7% showing vertigo while 143 hypertensive patients with 88.3% show no sign of vertigo.

A pie chart was also made to demonstrate the Frequency and percentage of patients with Presenting Complaints showed that vertigo (11.7%), Diabetes Mellitus (45.1 %), Dementia (4.3%) appeared with Cerebral Infarction. We Produced a table where we separated infarction on the basis of NO infarction (53.7%) Numbers of infarction One (16.7%), Two (2.5%) and Multiple (27.2%) collectively (46.4%) Appeared with cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients.

Table 5: Number Of Infarctions

Number of Infarctions	Frequency	Percentage %
No	87	53.7%
One	27	16.7%
Two	4	2.5%
Multiple	44	27.2%

We separated infarction on the basis of NO infarction (53.7%) Numbers of infarction One (16.7%), Two (2.5%) and Multiple (27.2%) collectively (46.4%) Appeared with cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients.

At first we produced a table where we separated the subjects on the basis of their age criteria (Table 1), (40-91 years) Then in the second table we grouped the same subjects on the basis of their sex (77 males, 47.5% & 85 females, 52.5%) calculating their frequency and percentage (Table 2), We calculated their standard deviations and mean values. The data Collected was tabulated in tables, as the purpose of this study is to rule out cerebral infarction in hypertensive patients as it is one of the major cause of mortality among the hypertensive patients.

Discussion

It was a Descriptive study on the topic of cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients on MRI. It was performed on the Lahore population in 2019. The main purpose of this research is to rule out cerebral infarction in hypertensive patients as it is one of the major cause of mortality among the hypertensive patients and Magnetic Resonance Imaging does provide sufficient information regarding cerebral infarction earlier studies used computed tomography for the evaluation of cerebral infarction. At that time, the results acquired by CT & MRI were nearly equivalent, but if we are talking about modern-day technology then MRI has surpassed in advancement and has become the modality of choice for imaging cerebral infarction. This research report aims

to acquire data about cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients on MRI. We aim to define a somewhat proper relationship between cerebral infarction and hypertensive patients using magnetic resonance imaging. Despite its significance Majority of the work done on cerebral infarction is by CT, although MRIs are more detailed in their images We examined 77 males and 85 females in the radiology department of AL-Razi Health Care Center Lahore. Population entered for MRI Head Scan examination were minimum 40 years and maximum 91 years old with the mean of 67.35

According to Ali Guerrmazi research published in 2003 Rapid and precise evaluation is crucial but often hard as neurological manifestations are usually disease-specific. Presenting the imagery characteristic of the central nervous system Neurological imaging in conjunction with electrophysiological research as well as blood and cerebrospinal fluid investigations may be useful to diagnose Many of these complications and the differentiation between the underlying disease manifestations (Guermazi A, 2003)

According to DA Decker research published in 2018 in a study concluded That cerebrovascular diseases, including ischemic and hemorrhagic circumstances, are the world's leading causes of death and disability. Because ischemic types of cerebrovascular disease with atherothrombosis are the most prevalent cause of stroke syndromes, cerebral infarction patterns are assessed. Hypertensive vascular disease contributes to the growth of atherosclerosis and arteriolosclerosis and is the leading cause of acute cerebral hemorrhage and lacunar infarction, both caused by profound penetration artery harm (Decker DA, 2018).

Another study investigated in 2017. It is a medical emergency with potentially devastating disease risk on an acute intracerebral hemorrhage. ICH is the second leading form of stroke after an ischemic stroke. Bleeding may result from multiple etiologies within the brain parenchyma. Though there are also other risk factors, hypertension is by far, the major risk factor for ICH (Alerhand Stephen, 2017).

Another of the study was conducted on the topic of Hypertension as a Risk Factor for sponataneous Intracerebral hemorrhage The study showed that To assess relative risk, the cases are correlated with samples with and without hypertension derived from the blood pressure analysis (n = 16,204). The relative risk of intracerebral hemorrhage was 3.9 (95 % maximum likelihood, 2.7 to 5.7) for the presence of prior hypertension. The relative risk was 5.4 (3.7 to 7.9) for the comprehensive definition of hypertension. Relative risk for black hypertension(= 4.4), age beyond 70 (= 7), previous cerebral infarction (= 22) and diabetes (= 3) was also established. We conclude that, particularly in whites, the word "hypertensive hemorrhage" should be used very selectively. and propose that hyperten And say that hypertension should be considered one of several primary risk factors for spontaneous intracerebral hemorrhage. (Brott TH ,1986)

Another study was performed on the topic of cerebral infarction in Young Adults Results showed Of the 428 first strokes, 212 (49.5%) had at least one reasonable cause, 80 (18.7%) had no reasonable grounds but at least one possible cause, and 136 (31.8%) had no probable or possible cause established Of the 212 that have a minimum of a likely cause, coronary embolism (31.1%), atherosclerotic and other (19.8%), oral contraceptive use (5.2%), large artery atherosclerotic disorder (3.8%), and migraine (1.4%) were reported. Small vessel disease (19.8%), nonatherosclerotic vasculopathy (11.3%), illegal drug use (9.4%), They also found that the most common cerebral infarction etiologies among young adults were in this hospital-based database within an area marked by racial/ethnic diversity, cardiac infarction, atherosclerotic and other causes, and lacunar strokes. Up to one-third of both the first and persistent strokes had no cause reported. (S.J.Kittner, 1998).

A study performed in 1994 their objective was To evaluate hypertensive cerebral involvement before cerebrovascular accidents. Our selection criteria were observed in 58 patients with hypertension, 11 patients with borderline hypertension, 15 hypertensive patients with cerebral infarction, and 58 normotensive controls. Researchers found that in both the symptomatic and asymptomatic hemispheres of the hypertensive patients, including cerebral infarction, the borderline hypertensive patients are greater than that. Two risk factors for cerebral atherosclerosis (age and hypertension) have been negatively correlated with cerebrovascular CO₂ reactivity in subjects without cerebral infarction. Concluded that hypertension impaired the microvascular

permeability of the brain before cerebrovascular injuries occurred and its influence depended on the degree to which other target organs were involved (Maeda H,1994).

Another study performed in Osaka University Hospital 2017 study data showed that MRI analysis of the brain examined 108 consecutive outpatients without a record of stroke. These included 66 patients with critical hypertension (63±9 years of age; mean±SD) and 42 age-grouped normotensive subjects (61±9 years of age). Careful analysis and comprehensive neurological tests showed that no subject had neurological problems and signs and history of stroke, including transient ischemic attack. MRI studies had been performed mainly to evaluate non-specific neurological symptoms (i.e., migraine, lightheadedness, dizziness, Hypertension). Hypertension was diagnosed to patients in the sitting position if patient blood pressure reached 160 mm Hg systolic/95 mm Hg diastolic. Selected risk factors included diabetes mellitus, hypercholesterolemia, daily intake of alcohol, heavy smoking of cigarettes, obesity (body mass index > 25), heart disease (arrhythmia or ischemic heart disease), hyperuricemia (serum uric acid > 7.0 mg/dl or medication) and elevated hematocrits (> 46%). In 45 of the 108 subjects analyzed (42%), SCI was observed. A total of 216 SCI lesions have been detected. In hypertensive patients, the frequency of SCI appears to be higher (47%) than normotensive patients (33%). The incidence of hypertensive patients increased substantially from 27% in the 50s, 44% in the 60s and 87% in the 70s, while there was no marked increase in normotensive patients. (H Hougaku,1992)

In contrast our analyzed data showed the mean values and the standard deviations of the data acquired. The mean values among the age of patients and standard deviation in subjects is 67.35±10.937. The frequency and percentage of patients complaining showed that vertigo (11.7%), Diabetes Mellitus (45.1%), Dementia (4.3%) appeared with Cerebral Infarction. We produced a table where we separated infarction on the basis of NO infarction (53.7%), Numbers of infarction One (16.7%), Two (2.5%), and Multiple (27.2%) collectively (46.4%) appeared with cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients. The results indicated that 46.4% appeared with cerebral infarction triggered by hypertension and that hypertension can be the cause of cerebral infarction and can lead to morbidity and mortality, particularly in adults.

Conclusion

It is concluded that there was no such prominent evaluation among hypertensive patients showing cerebral infarction. Although these results show that hypertension can be the cause of cerebral infarction and can lead to morbidity and mortality, particularly in adults. This study incorporates up to the minute data regarding cerebral infarction among hypertensive patients on magnetic resonance imaging; it is the modality of choice for imaging cerebral infarction. It provided a trend that needs to be validated with further studies and analysis on a bigger population.

References

- Liu H. Application of multimodal CT examination in acute cerebral infarction. *Guoji Naoxueguanbing Zazhi*. 2011;19(09):687-93.
- Hurley MC, Soltanolkotabi M, Ansari S. Neuroimaging in acute stroke: choosing the right patient for neurointervention. *Techniques in vascular and interventional radiology* 2012;15(1):19-32
- Šaňák D, Nosál V, Horák D, Bártková A, Zeleňák K, Herzig R, et al. Impact of diffusion-weighted MRI-measured initial cerebral infarction volume on clinical outcome in acute stroke patients with middle cerebral artery occlusion treated by thrombolysis. *Neuroradiology* 2006;48(9):632-9.
- Tong D, Yenari M, Albers G, O'Brien M, Marks M, Moseley M. Correlation of perfusion- and diffusion-weighted MRI with NIHSS score in acute (< 6.5 hour) ischemic stroke. *Neurology* 1998;50(4):864-9
- Hand P, Wardlaw J, Rivers C, Armitage P, Bastin M, Lindley R, et al. MR diffusion-weighted imaging and outcome prediction after ischemic stroke. *Neurology* 2006;66(8):1159-63
- Vermeer SE, Longstreth Jr WT, Koudstaal PJ. Silent brain infarcts: a systematic review. *The Lancet Neurology* 2007;6(7):611-9.
- Kesavadas C, Fiorelli M, Gupta A, Pantano P, Bozzao L, Kapilamoorthy T. Diffusion weighted magnetic resonance imaging in acute ischemic stroke. *Indian Journal of Radiology and Imaging* 2003;13(4):433-40.

- Bhagavati S, Choi J. Can Transient Drop in Blood Pressure in High-Risk Hypertensive Patients Cause Small Cerebral Infarcts? *ISRN Stroke* 2013;2013.
- Hoshida S, Kario K, Mitsuhashi T, Sato Y, Umeda Y, Katsuki T, et al. Different patterns of silent cerebral infarct in patients with coronary artery disease or hypertension. *American journal of hypertension* 2001;14(6):509-15.
- Calamante F, Yim PJ, Cebral JR. Estimation of bolus dispersion effects in perfusion MRI using image-based computational fluid dynamics. *Neuroimage* 2003;19(2):341-53
- Decker DA, Perry A, Yachnis AT. Vascular and ischemic disorders. In: *Practical Surgical Neuropathology: A Diagnostic Approach*: Elsevier; 2018. p. 633-58.
- Guermazi A, Miaux Y, Lafitte F, Zahar JR, Gluckman E. CT and MR imaging of central nervous system effects of therapy in patients treated for hematological malignancies. *European radiology* 2003;13(6):L202-L14
- Alerhand S, Lay C. Spontaneous intracerebral hemorrhage. *Emergency Medicine Clinics*. 2017 Nov 1;35(4):825-45.
- Brott TH, Thalinger KA, Hertzberg VI. Hypertension as a risk factor for spontaneous intracerebral hemorrhage. *Stroke*. 1986 Nov;17(6):1078-83.
- Maeda H, Matsumoto M, Handa N, Hougaku H, Ogawa S, Itoh T, Tsukamoto Y, Kamada T. Reactivity of cerebral blood flow to carbon dioxide in hypertensive patients: evaluation by the transcranial Doppler method. *Journal of hypertension*. 1994 Feb;12(2):191-7.
- Kittner SJ, Stern BJ, Wozniak M, Buchholz DW, Earley CJ, Feeser BR, Johnson CJ, Macko RF, McCarter RJ, Price TR, Sherwin R. Cerebral infarction in young adults: the Baltimore-Washington cooperative young stroke study. *Neurology*. 1998 Apr 1;50(4):890-4.
- Hougaku H, Matsumoto M, Kitagawa K, Harada K, Oku N, Itoh T, Maeda H, Handa N, Kamada T. Silent cerebral infarction as a form of hypertensive target organ damage in the brain. *Hypertension*. 1992 Dec;20(6):816-20.